

THE MAIN ADVANTAGES AND DISADVANTAGES OF USING DIGITAL PEDAGOGY

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7650751>

Abstract. *The article presents the principles of rational and effective use of digital technologies, digital pedagogy, education information, information and communication technologies, virtual learning environment, and Web 2.0 technologies.*

Keywords: *digital technology, digital pedagogy, virtual learning environment, information and communication technologies, Web 2.0 Internet technologies, virtual technologies.*

Currently, digital technologies are rapidly developing in the world, and this process requires keeping up with the times by effectively using digital technologies in all areas. In today's era, when information reception and use, analysis, and transmission are increasingly developing, direct use of digital technologies in the education system is of great importance in increasing educational opportunities, quality of education, and educating socially active young people both intellectually and culturally. Currently, the main goal of pedagogical education is to train techno-pedagogues capable of developing, improving and implementing digital pedagogy. Teachers need to integrate technology into instruction by understanding their role in technology-focused classrooms and developing skills to use web technologies in practice.

Therefore, it is predicted that the new generation of pedagogical methodologies and teaching and learning approaches will focus on the individuality of students and will be a central tool in the personalization process of social networks. Integrating social media into institutional structures of education is expected to create individualized and easily adaptable academic pathways to meet the needs of each student. Maintaining a clear structure of educational goals based on curricula and combining them with new methods of digital control of the educational process and learning experience allows to increase the quality and efficiency of education, and at the same time has a positive effect on the motivation of students. Information and communication technologies (ICT) are increasingly common in school and university education, as well as in professional organizations, to integrate learning experiences.

Today's "digital approaches" allow students to see these emerging digital technologies head-on and introduce them to concepts such as blended learning, e-learning, multimedia, and more. It explains how digital technologies can be used both in the classroom and as a way to overcome time and geographical constraints in the classroom. Based on these processes, we will also consider the main advantages and disadvantages of using a digital conditions in teaching. Finally, we offer a selection of texts and links to websites to enable students to further explore the use of ICT.

Trainers and training organizations who are interested in e-learning and want to learn more about e-learning solutions may find learning management systems, online courses, and games and simulations.

A digital approach in education requires the use of information and communication technologies (ICT) to implement or improve the implementation of educational programs.

Digital tools can be used to facilitate classroom learning, supplement learning with additional materials that allow students to master the content taught, develop hands-on skills, or collaborate with other students. It consists of creating fully virtual learning environments in which learning, teaching and interaction take place online (distance learning). In addition, educational institutions that use digital approaches decide to use the advances in the world of digital conditions to develop their learning areas. Thus, the development of Web 2.0 technologies, applications, virtual spaces, and co-production content has resulted in several platforms and functions of interest for learning and teaching.

In conclusion, it can be said that the introduction of digital technologies in various fields, not only in the education system, plays a major role in the modernization of the country's education system. It serves to improve the organization of modern education and the effectiveness of education.

REFERENCES

1. Абдуқодиров А.А. Таълимда инновацион технологиялар. – Тошкент: Истеъдод, 2008. – 180 б.
2. Абдуқодиров А., Пардаев А. Таълим ва тарбияда замонавий педагогик технологиялардан фойдаланиш услубиёти. Тошкент. 2014 - й. 366 б.
3. Алексанков А.М. Четвертая промышленная революция и модернизация образования: международный опыт / А. М. Алексанков // Стратегические приоритеты. — 2017. — № 1 (13). — С. 53—69.
4. Бегимкулов У.Ш. Олий педагогик таълим тизимида замонавий ахборот ва коммуникация технологияларини жорий этишнинг илмий-педагогик асослари. Пед.фан.доктори дисс. –Т.: 2007. – Б.250.
5. Ибрагимова Г.Н. Интерфаол ўқитиш методлари ва технологиялари асосида талабаларнинг креативлик қобилиятларини ривожлантириш. Диссертация PhD: 13.00.01.-Тошкент. 2017.-130-б.
6. Бакиева, Ф. Р., Примкулова, А. А., & Мирзахмедова, Н. Д. (2020). Smart And Development Of Modern Education.